

SOP for Preparing Open Data Folders

For each publication we are required to provide an Open Data folder that gets deposited to the University. PhD students are also required to provide an Open Data folder for their theses. The Open Data folder should contain all data files used to produce the science in the publication. Typically, there should be data files for each of the figures in the manuscript and ESI. Data files should conform to FAIR guidelines (see doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18).

Open Data folders should be organized in the following general fashion. There should be subfolders for each of Computations, Compound Characterization, Optoelectronic Characterization, Devices/Photocatalysis/Sensing/etc. These top-level subfolders can be further divided. For instance, Optoelectronic Characterization can be subdivided into Electrochemistry and Photophysics.

Figure 1. Example of the organization of an Open Data Folder

Ensure that all compounds are named consistently throughout the Open Data Folder, do not mix compound number/compound name/labbook reaction number/compound nickname for different sections of the Open Data Folder.

In the **Computations subfolder**, a suggested organization is that each subfolder is named after each compound. Contained within should be the files associated with ground-state optimization, frequency calculations, TD-DFT type calculations, SOC-type calculations, etc. For each type of calculation there must be two files, the input file (.com or .gjf) and the .log output files. Do not include images/PPTX files or other files associated with the processing of computational data.

The **Compound Characterization subfolder** should contain subfolders for each of the compounds and the data contained within should mirror those in your Compound Characterization folder on the group server. Importantly, NMR data must contain the original FID files, the MNova and PDF files of the spectra. HRMS/EA/HPLC/GCMS should be PDF files. There is no need to provide the CIF files as these are handled separately in a submission to the CCDC.

The **Optoelectronic Characterization subfolder** may contain, if appropriate, a further set of subfolder divided by measurement type or compound name. Files that should be included are .CSV or .TXT files of the data used to generate the plots and the Origin files.

The **Applications subfolder** (such as OLEDs, Photocatalysis, Sensing) may contain, if appropriate, a further set of subfolders divided by measurement type or compound name. Files that should be included are .CSV or .TXT files of the data used to generate the plots and the Origin files.

Description of Open Data

You must also include an open data description text. Please adapt the following text to the specific study:

The open data folder includes four sub-folders: **Calculations**, **Characterization**, **Optoelectronics** and **Devices**.

The **Calculations** folder includes the .log and .com (or .gjf) files for investigated compounds.

The **Characterization** folder includes NMR (FID and MNova files), GCMS (PDF), HRMS (PDF) data of the intermediates and NMR (FID and MNova files), HRMS (PDF), EA (PDF) and HPLC (PDF) data of the compounds.

The **Optoelectronics** folder includes two sub-folders: **Electrochemistry** and **Photophysics**. The **Electrochemistry** folder includes the raw data of CV and DPV measurements (the CSV file saved from the instrument) and the Origin files used for plotting spectra. The **Photophysics** folder includes the raw data (the CSV file saved

from the instrument) and Origin files of UV-vis absorption spectra in solutions, SSPL, TRPL spectra and PLQY measurements in solutions and films. Other data should be included where relevant, such as ΔE_{ST} measurements, photostability studies, Stern-Volmer Quenching studies and optical gap measurements.

The **Devices** folder includes the raw data (the CSV file saved from the instrument) and Origin files of OLED measurements (EL spectra, *JVL* and EQE data).